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Indicators of the transition from the gold standard to a stable currency in the context of an international transformational crisis

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The institution of money, being a system-forming element, serves the functions of a universal indicator of the effectiveness of economic practices and an instrument for ensuring a country's financial security. Modern state money, having moved beyond commodity and symbolic forms, has transformed into information, which is distorted to accommodate the interests of major economic actors. In this regard, an urgent task arises to define the essence and form of money that, on the other hand, should meet the objectives of economic development amidst a global transformational crisis.

Materials and methods. Materials from scientific journals and proceedings of international conferences were used in the study. Methods employed in the study, included historical analysis of documents and data from past transitions, study of other countries' experiences, analysis of expert opinions on prospects and risks, and investigation of contemporary initiatives to create new currency mechanisms, such as CBDCs and blockchain.

Results. The study concludes that a return to a stable national currency, backed by both gold and those non-precious metals that have every reason to elevate their status as a means of backing money due to advancements in scientific and technological progress and a revision of international currency agreements of the past 20th century, is justified.

Conclusion. The study describes the historical role of gold as the foundation of financial systems and highlights the current crisis associated with the dollar-centric system, inequality, and resource depletion.

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INTRODUCTION

The historical gold standard is predominantly viewed unfavorably by economists and financial experts. Nevertheless, this system remained operational for a considerable duration. The United States maintained a gold-backed currency for nearly 180 years until the early 1970s.

The proposition to reinstate the gold standard generally faces widespread skepticism and criticism. However, several contemporary indicators suggest potential shifts in this direction. Notably, central banks have significantly increased gold acquisitions in recent years, with major purchasers including China, India, and Russia. These developments reflect growing apprehensions regarding the long-term stability of the US dollar and emerging signs of relative decline in US economic dominance.

The rising prominence of cryptocurrencies represents another relevant development, though typically without sufficient consideration of the crucial role price stability plays in facilitating commercial transactions and long-term contractual agreements.

Concurrently, escalating levels of both public and private debt continue to grow uncontrollably, creating preconditions for severe economic crises. Global debt now exceeds USD 300 trillion, representing approximately three times global GDP. Concurrently, initiatives led by BRICS nations, South Africa, and other states are gaining momentum. Illustratively, India commenced issuance of gold-backed sovereign bonds last year.

The contemporary relevance of gold standard reinstatement remains contentious. Advocates argue it would ensure financial stability, curb inflationary pressures, and enhance currency credibility by eliminating excessive money creation and speculative activities. Conversely, critics emphasize its constraints on economic policy flexibility and inadequate capacity for rapid response to economic crises and global challenges.

Bimetallism emerged during the 18th-19th centuries as a monetary system wherein currency was simultaneously backed by both gold and silver, aiming to enhance monetary stability and expand the monetary base.

A. Redish characterizes bimetallic standards as monetary regimes wherein gold and silver coins function as primary exchange media within an economy. The

concurrent circulation of two metallic currencies, with values maintaining a 10:16 ratio, expanded denominational options compared to monometallic systems, yet introduced new complications while addressing existing limitations [1].

L. H. Officer observes that bimetallism was formally abandoned in 1816 in favor of the gold standard, though a de facto bimetallic system persisted in Britain for several years around the turn of the 18th century [2].

The gold standard gained prominence during the 19th century as nations increasingly pegged their currencies to gold to establish monetary stability and confidence. The first international gold standard regime was established during the 1870s.

L. H. Officer describes the "classical gold standard" as the most renowned monetary system in history, whose period of dominance spanned approximately one-third of a century. According to this analysis, the system incorporated both stability-enhancing characteristics and instability-generating factors [3].

G. B. Pittaluga and E. Seghezza identify the gold standard's duration from 1871 to 1914. Prior to 1871, most developed economies operated under bimetallic systems requiring fixed gold-silver parity [4].

C. Berg contends that the 1929 economic crisis and subsequent Great Depression were significantly aggravated by the post-war readoption of the gold standard by numerous countries, contributing to global economic contraction. Sweden's abandonment of the gold standard in 1931 facilitated comparatively rapid economic recovery, aided by currency devaluation and innovative price-level targeting in monetary policy [5].

M. D. Bordo and F. E. Kydland posit that the practical evolution and operation of the gold standard diverged from the predictions of theoretical models in economics. Analyzing the works of John Maynard Keynes, the authors conclude that central banks effectively possessed significant policy autonomy under the gold standard due to the existence of fluctuation bands bounded by gold import and export points [6].

The primary inefficiency of the gold standard lies in its constrained monetary policy flexibility, which complicates economic regulation and crisis management. This fact has been noted by numerous researchers.

P. Spread argues that the gold standard proved ineffective in addressing trade deficits, as the United States and other countries neutralized gold inflows to maintain domestic price stability. The gold-exchange standard, introduced

to compensate for gold shortages, diluted the impact of gold-convertibility obligations on reserve-currency countries. Effectively, the gold standard yielded to a dollar standard [7].

W. Yan maintains that adherence to the gold standard constituted a significant obstacle to recovery from the Great Depression. The researcher found that countries with higher income inequality at the depression's onset maintained gold standard legislation longer than those with lower inequality [8].

Y. Gonjo observes that Keynes viewed managed currency as an instrument for combating unemployment while criticizing the classical gold standard. The author also quotes another economist, Jacques Rueff, characterizing the gold-exchange standard of his time as "the most absurd system of settlements imaginable" [9].

Y. Gonjo et al. indicate that Rueff opposed the gold-exchange standard from a position of "monetary orthodoxy", whereas Keynes advocated for a "modified gold standard" that would remove constraints on gold emission [10].

D. Glasner, analyzing Hayek's works, demonstrates that his early commitment to the gold standard led to policy recommendations inconsistent with his own theory, including apparent acceptance of deflation to preserve the standard. By 1935, Hayek's attachment to the gold standard had diminished, and he subsequently acknowledged that his opposition to monetary expansion aimed at stabilizing aggregate spending was erroneous and politically motivated [11].

The Bretton Woods system (post-1944) established fixed exchange rates against the US dollar, which was convertible to gold. It provided stability for international settlements but required stringent regulation and imposed constraints on foreign exchange operations.

Y. Gonjo further notes that various measures were implemented in the 1970s to sustain the Bretton Woods system, including the creation of Special Drawing Rights and a dual-tier gold price system. The adoption of floating exchange rates constituted a "result of a superpower's political choice aimed entirely at avoiding adjustment" [12].

N. Sussman and C. Wyplosz observe that the collapse of the Bretton Woods system marked the severance of the link between fiat money and gold, creating conditions permitting floating exchange rates. The dominance of the US dollar consequently intensified [13].

M. D. Bordo analyzes empirical evidence comparing the effectiveness of three monetary regimes: the classical gold standard, the Bretton Woods system, and the current floating exchange rate system. The author contends that successful fixed-rate regimes, beyond being founded on simple transparent rules, incorporated features that incentivized leader countries to enforce the rules and other nations to comply with them [14].

P. Benigno analyzes historical manifestations of inefficiency and instability in the international monetary system, spanning from the gold standard to contemporary “fiat” currency systems. The researcher contends that innovations arising from cryptocurrency competition and associated blockchain technology possess the potential to ameliorate this situation [15].

T. Bayoumi et al. document that currency crises in Europe and Mexico during the 1990s served as stark reminders of both the importance and fragility of international financial markets. The pre-1914 gold standard presents a significant challenge to the notion that open capital markets inherently generate instability. The authors provide a comprehensive survey of relevant applied research in international macroeconomics [16].

C. Li posits that an effective international monetary system must facilitate the development of international economic activity; provide adequate means for supporting international economic operations; help maintain confidence in international reserve assets; and enable effective balance of payments adjustment when imbalances occur [17].

M. C. Marcuzzo documents that in Europe, the necessity of ensuring adequate exchange rate stability within the international system of flexible exchange rates led European countries to develop exchange rate agreements, ultimately culminating in the establishment of the Economic and Monetary Union in 1999 [18].

R. C. Niles rejects the current fiat money system due to its propensity for inflation and economic cycles when managed by inept central banks. Comparing gold with Bitcoin, the author concludes that both assets are inherently non-inflationary due to their built-in constraints on new supply. The scholar proposes making Bitcoin more responsive to demand, thereby reducing its price volatility and potentially establishing it as “superior money” [19].

Source analysis indicates that a return to the gold standard is currently improbable due to its constraints on monetary policy flexibility, the necessity to manage economies within modern financial systems, and contemporary global challenges.

Various scholarly perspectives on international monetary systems have been examined. Many researchers believe innovations such as cryptocurrencies and blockchain technology could enhance the global monetary system. Some scholars propose considering gold and Bitcoin as alternatives without inflationary risks, while suggesting the potential for reducing Bitcoin's volatility through demand-side mechanisms.

Current indicators of transition from the gold standard toward a future stable currency include development of central bank digital currencies (CBDCs), implementation of blockchain technologies, enhanced international cooperation on monetary system regulation, and the pursuit of more flexible and transparent monetary governance mechanisms that ensure stability and adaptability within the modern economic environment.

The study is aimed at examining indicators enabling transition from the gold standard to a future stable currency within the context of international transformational crisis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The scientific articles from authoritative peer-reviewed journals (Frontiers in Economic History, Eastern Economic Journal, Comparative Economic Studies, IMF Economic Review, among others), along with proceedings from numerous international conferences, were used in the study.

The following methodological approaches were employed in the study: historical analysis (examining documents, regulatory frameworks, economic data, and case studies of past transitions); comparative analysis of national experiences from countries that underwent similar transformations, including their outcomes and lessons learned; analysis of perspectives from leading scholars and practitioners regarding prospects and risks; and investigation of contemporary initiatives to establish new monetary mechanisms (CBDCs, blockchain).

RESULTS

The subjective nature of modern money

The well-established scholarly thesis that the current phase of globalization, having reached a point of self-negation, is neither unique nor without alternatives, persuades us that the period of disillusionment with comprehensive state regulation

and planning is concluding. Leading economic actors are prepared to reject, albeit fragmentarily and gradually, the fundamental tenets of market fundamentalism. A significant motive for this ideological transformation is the evident failure of financial and currency markets to serve as sources of even economic growth, let alone economic development.

Rapid changes and constant innovations in the monetary sphere stimulate scholarly inquiry into the essence of new forms of money, their functions, significance, and role. Moreover, a practically revolutionary question arises: do money even exist today, and if they do, what exactly should be considered money?

Most economists would respond within the established framework of knowledge, defining money as a universal designated commodity that has gained recognition among the economic agents who utilize it. According to the classical view of K. Marx, a commodity constitutes a social relation [], implying that money inherently contains evaluative criteria due to the subjectivity of these relations [20].

The abandonment of money backed by real values, most often in the form of precious metals in 1971, accelerated its transformation from a universal commodity into arrangements based on trust between transaction participants. Given that the value and liquidity of the physical carrier of the object conventionally called money is practically negligible, it is precisely society's trust in the issuer (the state) of money that forms its foundation. However, beyond trust, citizen consent to use unbacked money is explained by the socio-economic project with corresponding macroeconomic parameters proposed by the state, often under pressure from major corporations. Consequently, modern money, particularly the US dollar as the global currency, has become the embodiment of a modern financial pyramid, with its backing determined by the symbolic capital of giant corporations and their capacity for global governance [21]. Since the recognized indicator of corporate economic power is market capitalization, understood as the value of their assets calculated based on stock market quotations, it is evident that both money itself and the entire modern market pricing mechanism embody subjectivity.

A significant intensification of the subjective nature of new money [22] occurred with the emergence of cryptocurrencies. These function as private payment instruments, are well-suited for quasi-economic purposes (computer games, servicing metaverses, etc.), and exhibit the most extreme volatility compared to all previously known means of payment and stores of value (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Bitcoin exchange rate from its inception to 2024 [23]

The necessity of currency stability was repeatedly emphasized by J. M. Keynes, who argued that at the level of individual commodity markets, the primary destabilizing factor is unreliable money, which leads to sudden loss of savings due to unemployment for some and speculative enrichment for others. At the level of the economic system as a whole, unstable money creates an unsolvable conundrum, particularly in measuring the outcomes of scientific and technological progress, since it is impossible to reliably compare physical output volumes produced at different times [24].

The reliability and stability of modern money, especially as a store of value, is essential for a healthy economic system for several reasons.

First, monetary stability guarantees the functionality of a mixed economic system, including through the formation of conditions for social and financial security. Such money can be termed “minted freedom” for citizens, provided by the monopoly issuer of money ensuring a medium of exchange with stable purchasing power [25].

Second, monetary stability is necessary to minimize direct losses for households, firms, and the state due to speculative currency fluctuations in the context of investments and savings. In other words, such money can be described as an instrument for the asymptotic reduction of transaction costs in financial market operations to zero.

Third, monetary stability is essential for reducing indirect losses to society as a whole from using “distorted” money, which, like a distorted signal, stimulates the production of more inherently unneeded goods, increases exploitation through unjustified extension of working hours, and generates superprofits for the financial elite. Continuing the list of negative consequences of using subjective unstable

money, it should be noted that expenditures recorded in national statistics increase as a result of addressing accidents, epidemics, floods, and implemented measures to alleviate social stress, declining national health indicators, and overall quality of life, which is then interpreted as economic growth [26].

In essence, the situation presents a paradox inherent in the use of subjective unstable money: its expanding volume progressively distorts the concept of progress, culminating in an absurdity.

Objective preconditions for utilizing a new gold standard

Common sense has always suggested that humanity should use stable money which, analogous to the base units of the International System of Units (SI) – kg, m, s, A, mol – would minimize transaction costs of exchange, serve as an effective investment instrument, and not act as an inflationary tax on the poor.

Interestingly, in 1928, the world-renowned English playwright B. Shaw, with characteristic Irish bluntness, remarked that under the capitalist system, everyone must choose between the natural stability of gold and the honesty of government ministers, and that, with all due respect to those gentlemen, it is better to trust gold [27]. It should be noted that over the past hundred years, nothing has fundamentally changed regarding the backing of and trust in money as a universal commodity. This thesis is clearly confirmed by modern cryptocurrency adherents, who are naively rediscovering the basic postulate of a commodity economy: money must be stable.

The turn towards stable money is a typical societal reaction to economic collapses resulting from the effective destruction of the national currency as an instrument for ensuring national financial security and stability. This was the case in Germany in the 1920s, in Latin America in the 1980s, in Japan in the 1990s, in Thailand, South Korea, Indonesia, and the Philippines in 1997, in Russia and Brazil in 1998, in Turkey in 2001, and in Argentina in 2002.

It is evident that the financial crises in Latin America, Southeast Asia, and Russia, despite their diverse regional and national specificities, are ultimately united by destructive monetary policies based on pegging the national currency's exchange rate to the US dollar. The sharp decline in exchange rates and an unacceptable contraction of the money supply resulted in economic crises largely of subjective origin. In this context, one cannot but agree with Harvard Professor B. Lindsey, who argues that "monetary policy is the minefield of modern economic life. The

importance of sound monetary policy cannot be overstated: over the past hundred years, only war has rivaled monetary policy errors in its destructive capacity" [28].

If the necessity of constructing or reforming an economic system utilizing stable money is beyond doubt, the question remains: what exactly should be considered stable, resilient, reliable money? Will gold-backed money unequivocally be stable under modern conditions, and what characteristics of such money would prevent it from being deemed a "barbarous relic", as J. M. Keynes asserted?

From this perspective, the answer may lie not merely in a new gold standard, but in a broader concept: purpose-specific commodity metallic money. The foundational idea of the gold standard would persist in such metallic money, and its use should be regulated by the state as an instrument for pricing key export commodities, facilitating international settlements, and directing state investments to achieve strategic macroeconomic objectives.

The global economic crisis, which entered an overt phase with the COVID-19 pandemic, exhibits all the hallmarks of a structural crisis. Today, the positions of the main players on the global economic stage, the sources of their dominance, and national priorities in domestic and foreign policy are undergoing significant change [29]. There is a discernible increase in state participation and regulation, consequently generating a need for predictable monetary policy. For instance, as early as 2012, representatives of the Republican Party in the US began discussing a return to the gold standard. In the autumn of 2022, a bill to restore the gold standard was introduced in the US House of Representatives, noting that over the past 22 years the US dollar had lost 30% of its purchasing power, and since the Federal Reserve Act of 1913, the national currency had "shed" 97% of its value [30].

In February 2023, the Central Bank of Russia announced its readiness to issue a gold token based on digital financial assets, intended for use in both international settlements and as a significant investment asset. In other words, for the first time in recent history, Russia will issue a financial asset backed by physical gold.

Prerequisites for expanding the group of precious metals in modern conditions

Amid the transformational crisis, Russia's response to the declared sanctions war has been a pivot to the East, where it has organized intensive trade in national currencies with all EAEU and Arab world countries, India, China, and Turkey. However, to establish long-term foundations for economic development in cooperation with

these partners, it is necessary to build systems for pricing, investment, insurance, and credit based on fundamentally different underlying assets. For millennia, the classical instrument for these purposes has been precious metals.

Currently, the largest exchanges trading precious metals, such as the London Metal Exchange, NYMEX and COMEX in New York, and TOCOM in Tokyo, classify gold, silver, palladium, and platinum as precious metals. The Russian National Standard adds another four platinum group metals: iridium, rhodium, ruthenium, and osmium [34].

However, the current transformational crisis, whose economic essence lies in the exhaustion of the capitalist model's potential – a model based on the exponential profit growth of the global financial elite through the exploitation of colonial economic spaces – will eventually conclude. Its positive outcome will be a complex of scientific, technological, and, crucially, financial prerequisites for the fourth energy transition. To date, 110 states, including the EU, the UK, South Korea, and Japan, intend to abandon hydrocarbon fuels in favor of renewable energy sources and achieve carbon neutrality by 2050, with China targeting 2060 [35].

In order to achieve these goals, for instance, the British company Xlinks plans to build a solar and wind power plant complex in Morocco, rivaling the capacity of modern thermal power stations, and has consequently initiated the laying of a submarine cable [36].

It is noteworthy that copper and nickel are used in the production of submarine cables, batteries, generators, motherboards, and simply most wires, leading to the assertion that the entire real green energy sector, computing technologies, and many other advanced industries rest on the shoulders of these giant metals. Certainly, the list of valuable future metals is more extensive and includes cobalt, palladium, lithium, zinc, graphite, and rare earth metals. Each of these metals warrants separate, serious economic analysis from the perspective of global economic powers' interaction strategies; however, copper and nickel serve as a kind of composite matrix into which the other elements are added. In this context, it is logical to assume that copper and nickel have a realistic chance of entering the group of precious metals of the 21st century.

The key properties of copper and nickel that justify their classification as precious metals are their rarity in nature, inertness in reactions with hydrochloric acid, corrosion resistance, and partially, their jewelry value with the caveat that copper's corrosion

resistance is achieved through nickel plating, and nickel's relatively low jewelry value is explained by its toxicity.

Regarding the rarity of copper and nickel as “candidates” for precious metals, it is worth noting a certain monopoly of Chile, which accounts for over 30% of global copper ore reserves. The country is the leader in mining this metal, with an annual output of approximately 6 million tons. Globally, there are about 5,600 billion tons of copper, of which 2,100 billion tons are proven reserves, and 870 million tons of the proven reserves constitute the current global copper stockpile. The annual global copper production exceeds 20 million tons, with the Russian Federation contributing 4% [37]. It should be noted that despite Chile's unequivocal leadership at present, future copper mining in the country may become more challenging due to a number of reasons, including water supply issues and the depletion of deposits. These trends are confirmed by the nucleonic increase in development costs for Chilean copper deposits.

Global nickel reserves are estimated at 300 million tons, of which 89 million tons are proven. In terms of production, the Russian Federation ranks third globally, behind Indonesia and the Philippines. In Russia, copper-nickel ore deposits are concentrated primarily in the Urals, Krasnoyarsk Krai, and the Murmansk region. Significant volumes of mined copper and nickel meet the growing global demand for these resources. Confident leadership among copper consumers has long belonged to China, followed by the USA, Hong Kong, and Japan. Germany and South Korea are not far behind [38]. Note that most of these countries are leaders in the fourth energy transition, which may serve as confirmation of the importance and value of copper and nickel in the modern world.

It should be noted that a precedent for the transition of an exchange-traded commodity to precious metal status already occurred in 2010 with palladium, a consequence of rising demand for this metal due to its unique combination of properties and rarity. Since 2006, palladium has appreciated almost sixfold and became the most expensive precious metal, although trends indicate a price parity between gold and palladium in 2023 [39]. The main application areas for palladium, besides electronics, dentistry, and the jewelry industry, are catalysts in gasoline engines used to reduce toxic emissions. These facts further confirm the thesis regarding the changing configuration of the precious metals basket in light of the transition to a green economy.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Gold has historically embodied wealth and served as the foundation of the financial system throughout human history. The monetary systems of the 19th and 20th centuries were organized as gold coin, gold bullion, and gold-dollar standards, while since the 1980s, the petrodollar has replaced gold as the mechanism controlling the emission of global fiat currencies.

The current dollar-centric system of global debt, characterized by unprecedented wealth stratification at both micro and mega levels, predatory exploitation of natural resources, and operating under the direction of transnational capital, has exhausted its potential.

Russia, possessing the world's most resource-rich territory, has a clear opportunity to construct an economic system independent of the global project, based on mutually beneficial trade and technological cooperation, and anchored in stable money. According to calculations by specialists from the major financial group Credit Suisse, pegging the price of two barrels of oil to one gram of gold would double the dollar price of gold [40]. Such a step is entirely feasible and would fundamentally reshape the configuration of global economic power centers in favor of Russia.

Gold as a foundation for the national currency has repeatedly rescued Russia. Count S.Y. Witte's gold ruble accelerated capitalist accumulation, though its flip side was the tethering of Russian industry and banks to Western capital. The post-war Soviet gold ruble of the 1950s, in addition to its metallic backing (with a gold content of 0.222168 grams of pure metal per ruble), was supported by the entire material wealth of the nation against the backdrop of the emergence and rapid growth of the gold mining industry. It became the basis for the USSR's unprecedented space, nuclear, and energy projects. The gold ruble ceased to exist following the 1961 monetary reform, which initiated the process of transforming the Soviet, and post-1991 Russian, economy into a raw materials periphery on the international economic map.

By 2022, objective conditions had emerged for the return to a gold ruble, primarily as a reliable investment instrument amid global economic turbulence within the context of a transformational crisis.

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